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A CHECKLIST OF SCIARID SPECIES (DIPTERA, SCIARIDAE) OF THE BROAD-LEAVED FOREST ZONE OF UKRAINE AND THE UKRAINIAN CARPATHIANS

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Babytskiy, A. A checklist of sciarid species (Diptera, Sciaridae) of the Broad-Leaved Forest zone of Ukraine and the Ukrainian Carpathians. — An annotated checklist of 90 sciarid species recorded from the Broad-Leaved Forest zone of Ukraine and the Ukrainian Carpathians is presented. Of these, 58 species are new records for the region or are confirmations of historical records based on new material. The remaining 32 species, known from the literature, were not re-collected during the present study.

Key words: dark-winged fungus gnats, species list, new records, Broad-Leaved Forest zone of Ukraine, Ukrainian Carpathians.

Бабицький, А. Анотований список видів сціарид (Diptera, Sciaridae) зони широколистяних лісів України та Українських Карпат. — Наведено анотований список 90 видів сціарид, зареєстрованих у зоні широколистяних лісів України та Українських Карпат. З них 58 видів є новими для регіону або є підтвердженням літературних вказівок на основі нового матеріалу. Решту 32 види, відомі за літературними даними, не було зібрано під час цього дослідження.

Ключові слова: тінювкові грибні комариків, список видів, нові знахідки, зона широколистяних лісів України, Українські Карпати.

Introduction

The Sciaridae Billberg, 1820 (Diptera), commonly known as black fungus gnats, are a species-rich family of small to medium-sized (body length up to 8 mm in imago), predominantly dark-coloured insects within the order Diptera. Ecologically, they are significant decomposers, with larvae typically developing in decaying organic matter, such as leaf litter and rotting wood, where they feed on fungal hyphae. While their typical habitats include shaded forests and wet meadows, some species have adapted to anthropogenic ecosystems, becoming synanthropic and occasionally reaching pest status in greenhouses and mushroom farms.

Historical records of sciarid fauna in the Broad-Leaved Forest zone of Ukraine and the Ukrainian Carpathians are sparse. Early investigations were conducted by Nowicki (1864, 1865, 1868) and Wierzejski (cited in Winnertz, 1868) in Podolia (modern Ternopil and Lviv Regions). More recent studies include those by Mamaev,

Krivosheina, and Dmitrieva in Transcarpathia (Zakarpatska Region) (Mohrig et al., 1989a, 1989b, 1990) and by Osmola (1970), who studied the development of *Pnyxia scabiei* (Hopkins, 1895) in potato fields and warehouses in the western regions of Ukraine, excluding the Carpathians. Additionally, Verkhratskyi (1864) documented the “military worm” phenomenon—mass migrations of sciarid larvae—in what is now the Lviv or Ivano-Frankivsk Regions. Based on this cumulative historical literature, a total of 47 species belonging to 14 genera were previously recorded for the study area. This study aims to update and significantly expand the knowledge of Sciaridae in this under-researched region.

Material and Methods

Specimens for this study were collected during field expeditions conducted between 2015 and 2022. Adult sciarids were captured using a standard sweep net and an

aspirator. The collected material was immediately preserved in 5 mL vials containing 70% ethanol.

For morphological identification, male specimens were processed in the laboratory by dehydration in absolute ethanol, followed by mounting on glass slides using Euparal as a mounting medium. Taxonomic examination was performed using MBS-9 and PZO Biolar microscopes. All examined material is deposited in the Sciaridae collection of the I.I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv (SIZK). The collection data have been made publicly available through the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and the Ukrainian Biodiversity Information Network (UkrBIN) portals.

Results

To date, the checklist of Sciaridae for the Broad-Leaved Forest zone of Ukraine and the Ukrainian Carpathians has been expanded to 90 species. Of these, 58 species represent new records for the region (marked with asterisk*) or are confirmations of historical records based on newly collected material. The remaining 32 species, known exclusively from historical literature, were not re-collected during our surveys. Based on the habitat diversity and the results of this study, it is estimated that the total species richness of Sciaridae in the region may be at least 200 species, highlighting the need for further research.

Bradysia alpicola (Winnertz, 1867)

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Zakarpatska.

Bradysia angustocularis Mohrig & Krivosheina, 1989

Babytskiy et al., 2020, 2022.

Material. Volyn: Turiisk, 187 m a.s.l., 51.079814° N, 24.530391° E; 01.05.2015, 4 ♂, 1 ♀; 02.05.2015, 1 ♂; 03.05.2015, 2 ♂; 04.05.2015, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Volyn.

Bradysia bicolor (Meigen, 1818)

Nowicki, 1864, 1865; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Lviv.

Bradysia brevispina Tuomikoski, 1960 (Fig. 1)

Babytskiy et al., 2020, 2022.

Material. Volyn: near Sokyrychi, 209 m a.s.l., 50.87516° N, 025.51393° E; 28.06.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Volyn.

Bradysia cinerascens (Grzegorzek, 1884) (Fig. 2)

Babytskiy et al. 2020, 2022.

Material. Lviv: near Stare Selo, 340 m a.s.l., 49.21899° N, 24.40241° E; 13.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Klubochyn, 213 m a.s.l., 50.96447° N, 25.77727° E; 27.06.2017, 1 ♂; near Klubochyn, 204 m a.s.l., 50.96230° N, 25.83071° E; 27.06.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy, Lviv, Volyn.

Bradysia fungicola (Winnertz, 1867) (Fig. 3)

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Luchka, 375 m a.s.l., 49.40917° N, 25.61360° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂; near Strusiv, 349 m a.s.l., 49.33878° N, 25.63311° E; 19.06.2018, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Zhabka, 211 m a.s.l., 50.81919° N, 25.43038° E; 29.06.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Kyiv, Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpatska.

Bradysia impatiens (Johannsen, 1912)

Babytskiy et al., 2019, 2022.

Material. Volyn: Turiisk, 150 m a.s.l., 51.080061° N, 24.530237° E; 25–26.10.2015, 3 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Volyn.

Bradysia leucopeza Mohrig & Mamaev, 1989

Mohrig, Krivosheina & Mamaev, 1989b; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Bradysia longispina Mohrig & Mamaev, 1989

Mohrig, Krivosheina & Mamaev, 1989a; Rudzinski & Ševčík, 2012; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Bradysia lobata Hondru, 1968

Babytskiy, Rubanovska & Bezsmertna, 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Luchka, 340 m a.s.l., 49.40547° N, 25.61313° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

Bradysia nitidicollis (Meigen, 1818)

Nowicki, 1864, 1865; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Lviv.

Bradysia placida (Winnertz, 1867)

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Lviv: near Stare Selo, 340 m a.s.l., 49.21899° N, 24.40241° E; 13.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Rivne:** near Romeiky, 165 m a.s.l., 51.272667° N, 26.171944° E; 10.09.2017, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** Solovychi, 181 m a.s.l., 51.06260° N, 24.48169° E; 30.04.2018, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Lviv, Rivne, Volyn.

Bradysia polonica (Lengersdorf, 1929)

Babytskiy et al., 2020, 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Mykulyntsi, 282 m a.s.l., 49.403088° N, 25.608273° E; 28.06.2014, 2 ♂; near Stinka, 200 m a.s.l., 48.91482° N, 25.23508° E; 09.08.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

Bradysia procera (Winnertz, 1868)

Winnertz, 1868; Menzel & Mohrig, 1998, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil Reg (“Podolien”—Podilska Vysocyna in the southwestern part of the country).

Bradysia tilicola (Loew, 1850)*

Material. Volyn: Turiisk, 185 m a.s.l., 51.07998° N, 24.53032° E; 06.08.2015, 1 ♂, 150 m a.s.l., 51.080061° N, 24.530237° E; 25–26.10.2015, 2 ♂, 150 m a.s.l., 51.080076° N, 24.530083° E; 05.12.2016,

Figures 1–15. Hypopygia, ventral view (scale bare 0.2 mm). 1—*Bradysia brevispina* Tuomikoski, 1960, 2—*B. cinerascens* (Grzegorzek, 1884), 3—*B. fungicola* (Winnertz, 1867), 4—*Corynoptera dentata* (Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936), 5—*Co. furcifera* Mohrig & Mamaev, 1987, 6—*Co. luteofusca* (Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936), 7—*Co. membranigera* (Kieffer, 1903), 8—*Co. tetrachaeta* Tuomikoski, 1960, 9—*Cratyna (Cratyna) ambigua* (Lengersdorf, 1934), 10—*Cr. (Peyerimhoffia) vagabunda* (Winnertz, 1867), 11—*Ctenosciara hyalipennis* (Meigen, 1804), 12—*Leptosciarella (Leptosciarella) scutellata* (Staeger, 1840), 13—*Hemineurina venosa* (Staeger, 1840), 14—*Lycoriella lundstromi* (Frey, 1948), 15—*Pseudolycoriella (Pseudolycoriella) paludum* (Frey, 1948).

1 ♂, 186 m a.s.l., 51.07998° N, 24.53032° E; 06.04.2018, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Volyn.

***Bradysia trivittata* (Staeger, 1840)**

Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Skomorokhy, 203 m a.s.l., 48.90773° N, 25.39594° E; 09.08.2016, 1 ♂; near Kasperivtsi, 192 m a.s.l., 48.68012° N, 25.85049° E; 22.06.2018, 1 ♂; Mykulyntsi, 335 m a.s.l., 49.40111° N,

25.60138° E; 09.07.2018, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Solovychi, 181 m a.s.l., 51.06260° N, 24.48169° E; 08.08.2015, 1 ♂; 12.08.2015, 1 ♂; Solovychi, 181 m a.s.l., 51.06260° N, 24.48169° E; 30.04.2018; 29 ♂; near Svitile, 166 m a.s.l., 51.255722° N, 25.294125° E; 30.09.2018, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Kharkiv, Kyiv, Odesa, Ternopil, Volyn.

***Bradysia vagans* (Winnertz, 1868)**

Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil Reg (“Podolien” — Podilska Vysocyna in the southwestern part of the country).

***Bradysia urticae* Mohrig & Menzel, 1992**

Babytskiy, Rubanovska & Bezsmertna, 2022.

Material. Ternopil: Mykulyntsi, 296 m a.s.l., 49.40126° N, 25.60140° E; 19–21.06.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

***Claustropyga abblanda* (Freeman, 1983)**

Hippan, Vilkamaa & Mohrig, 2003; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Claustropyga clausa* (Tuomikoski, 1960)**

Krivoshaina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Claustropyga ctenophora* Hippan, Vilkamaa & Mohrig, 2003**

Hippan, Vilkamaa & Mohrig, 2003; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Corynoptera bulgarica* (Mohrig & Mamaev, 1992)**

Hippan & Vilkamaa, 1994; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Corynoptera dentata* (Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936) (Fig. 4)**

Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Kasperivtsi, 203 m a.s.l., 48.67661° N, 25.85291° E; 22.06.2018, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Klubochyn, 204 m a.s.l., 50.96230° N, 25.83071° E; 27.06.2017, 1 ♂; Between Berestiane and Kholonevychi, 175 m a.s.l., 50.99890° N, 25.93088° E; 28.06.2017, 3 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Volyn, Kyiv, Ternopil.

***Corynoptera dentiforceps* (Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936)**

Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Hippan & Vilkamaa, 1994; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Volyn: Turiisk 187 m a.s.l., 51.079814° N, 24.530391° E; 04.05.2015, 1 ♂; 185 m a.s.l., 51.079814° N, 24.530391° E; 19.08.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Volyn.

***Corynoptera fatigans* (Johannsen, 1912)**

Babytskiy et al., 2019, 2022.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: Between Nezvesko and Luka, 168 m a.s.l., 48.78383° N, 25.25209° E; 10.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Ternopil:** Mykulyntsi, 296 m a.s.l., 49.40126° N, 25.60140° E; 19–21.06.2016, 2 ♂; near Pachorna, 143 m a.s.l., 48.66650° N, 25.67790° E; 31.07.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk, Ternopil.

***Corynoptera flavicauda* (Zetterstedt, 1855)**

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Luchka, 329 m a.s.l., 49.40437° N, 25.61119° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ternopil.

***Corynoptera furcifera* Mohrig & Mamaev, 1987 (Fig. 5)**

Babytskiy & Bezsmertna, 2021; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Volyn: near Klubochyn, 204 m a.s.l., 50.96230° N, 25.83071° E; 27.06.2017, 1 ♂; near Sokyrychi, 209 m a.s.l., 50.87516° N, 25.51393° E; 28.06.2017, 1 ♂; near Zhabka, 211 m a.s.l., 50.81919° N, 25.43038° E; 29.06.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Volyn.

***Corynoptera hypopygialis* (Lengersdorf, 1926)**

Babytskiy et al., 2019, 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Luchka, 329 m a.s.l., 49.40437° N, 25.61119° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

***Corynoptera inundata* Fritz, 1982**

Camaño Portela et al., 2008; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Skomorokhy, 203 m a.s.l., 48.90773° N, 25.39594° E; 09.08.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

***Corynoptera luteofusca* (Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936) (Fig. 6)**

Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936; Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Hippan, Vilkamaa & Heller, 2010; Mohrig et al., 2012; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Volyn: near Zhabka, 211 m a.s.l., 50.81919° N, 25.43038° E; 29.06.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Volyn.

***Corynoptera membranigera* (Kieffer, 1903) (Fig. 7)**

Babytskiy, Zueva & Bezsmertna, 2018a; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: Between Nezvesko and Luka, 168 m a.s.l., 48.78383° N, 25.25209° E; 10.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Ternopil:** near Luchka, Fruit body of *Fuligo septica* f. *flava*: 337 m a.s.l., 49.40601° N, 25.61581° E; 03.07.2015, 9 ♂; 337 m a.s.l., 49.40572° N, 25.61362° E; 03.07.2015, 1 ♂; Fruit body of *Russula* sp.: 337 m a.s.l., 49.40593° N, 25.61580° E; 03.07.2015, 3 ♂, 1 ♀; Fruit body of *Neoboletus luridiformis*: 342 m a.s.l., 49.40546° N, 25.61394° E; 06.07.2015, 2 ♂; 18.06.2018; 15 ♂; near Strusiv, 347 m a.s.l., 49.33881° N, 25.63246° E; 19.06.2018, 1 ♂; 349 m a.s.l., 49.33878° N, 25.63311° E; 19.06.2018, 6 ♂; 355 m a.s.l., 49.33839° N, 25.63538° E; 19.06.2018, 3 ♂; 361 m a.s.l., 49.33764° N, 25.63538° E; 19.06.2018, 2 ♂; 374 m a.s.l., 49.33638° N, 25.63387° E; 19.06.2018, 3 ♂; 408 m a.s.l., 49.34376° N, 25.62999° E; 30.06.2018, 3 ♂; 378 m a.s.l., 49.33495° N, 25.63931° E; 30.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Luchka 342 m a.s.l., 49.40665° N, 25.61123° E; 20.06.2018, 1 ♂; 359 m a.s.l., 49.40715° N, 25.61195° E; 20.06.2018, 4 ♂; 373 m a.s.l., 49.40878° N, 25.61436° E; 20.06.2018, 1 ♂; 338 m a.s.l., 49.40443° N, 25.61215° E; 27.06.2018, 10 ♂; near Druzhba, 370 m a.s.l., 49.34654° N, 25.66220° E; 28.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Volia 361 m a.s.l., 49.38776° N, 25.62919° E; 02.07.2018, 1 ♂; 346 m a.s.l., 49.38903° N, 25.62634° E; 02.07.2018, 1 ♂; Kosmyryn, 191 m a.s.l., 48.88371° N, 25.23212° E; 18.07.2018, 1 ♂; Hutsko, 419 m a.s.l., 49.40352° N, 24.83669° E; 16.07.2019, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Klubochyn, 213 m a.s.l., 50.96447° N, 25.77727° E; 27.06.2017, 1 ♂; 212 m a.s.l., 50.96522° N, 25.77657° E; 27.06.2017, 1 ♂; near Sokyrychi, 209 m a.s.l., 50.87516° N, 25.51393° E; 28.06.2017, 3 ♂; near Zhabka, 228 m a.s.l., 50.81466° N, 25.42506° E; 29.06.2017, 1 ♂; **Zakarpatska:** near Mala Uholka, 475 m a.s.l., 48.25609° N, 23.62223° E; 02.08.2019, 1 ♂; 691 m a.s.l., 48.26364° N, 23.61694° E; 02.08.2019, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpatska.

***Corynoptera polana* Rudzinski, 2009**

Hippa, Vilkamaa & Heller, 2010; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Corynoptera praeparvula* Mohrig & Krivosheina, 1983**

Babytskiy et al., 2019, 2022.

Material. Volyn: near Solovychi, 181 m a.s.l., 51.06260° N, 24.48169° E; 08.08.2015, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Volyn.

***Corynoptera saetistyla* Mohrig & Krivosheina, 1985**

Hippa, Vilkamaa & Heller, 2010; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Corynoptera serena* (Winnertz, 1868)**

Winnertz, 1868; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil Reg (“Podolien” — Podilska Vysocyna in the southwestern part of the country).

***Corynoptera subparvula* Tuomikoski, 1960**

Babytskiy et al., 2019, 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Pachorna, 143 m a.s.l., 48.66650° N, 25.67790° E; 31.07.2017, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Solovychi, 181 m a.s.l., 51.06260° N, 24.48169° E; 08.08.2015, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Odesa, Volyn.

***Corynoptera tetrachaeta* Tuomikoski, 1960 (Fig. 8)**

Hippa, Vilkamaa & Heller, 2010; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Druzhba, 370 m a.s.l., 49.34526° N, 25.65677° E; 03.08.2017, 2 ♂; **Volyn:** near Zhabka, 228 m a.s.l., 50.81466° N, 25.42506° E; 29.06.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpatska.

***Corynoptera trepida* (Winnertz, 1867)**

Hippa, Vilkamaa & Heller, 2010; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Corynoptera tridentata* Hondru, 1968**

Hippa, Vilkamaa & Heller, 2010; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: Mykulyntsi, 296 m a.s.l., 49.40126° N, 25.60140° E; 19-21.06.2016, 2 ♂; near Luchka, 329 m a.s.l., 49.40437° N, 25.61119° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂; 338 m a.s.l., 49.40493° N, 25.61218° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂; 375 m a.s.l., 49.40917° N, 25.61360° E; 07.05.2017, 4 ♂; near Kasperivtsi, 171 m a.s.l., 48.67120° N, 25.85270° E; 22.06.2018, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Zakarpatska.

***Cratyna (Cratyna) ambigua* (Lengersdorf, 1934) (Fig. 9)**

Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936; Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Camaño Portela et al., 2008; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Lviv: near Stare Selo, 340 m a.s.l., 49.21899° N, 24.40241° E; 13.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Ternopil:** near Luchka, 329 m a.s.l., 49.40437° N, 25.61119° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂; near Strusiv, 361 m a.s.l., 49.33764° N, 25.63538° E; 19.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Luchka, 327 m a.s.l., 49.40446° N, 25.61120° E; 27.06.2018, 1 ♂; 338 m a.s.l., 49.40443° N, 25.61215° E; 27.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Strusiv, 408 m a.s.l., 49.34376° N, 25.62999° E; 30.06.2018, 2 ♂; near Volia 361 m a.s.l., 49.38776° N,

25.62919° E; 02.07.2018, 2 ♂; 352 m a.s.l., 49.40038° N, 25.62152° E; 02.07.2018, 2 ♂; **Volyn:** near Zhabka, 228 m a.s.l., 50.81466° N, 25.42506° E; 29.06.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Cherkasy, Lviv, Ternopil, Volyn.

***Cratyna (Cratyna) atra* Winnertz, 1867**

Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Cratyna (Cratyna) fulvicauda* (Felt, 1897)**

Babytskiy & Bezsmertna, 2021; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Kasperivtsi, 203 m a.s.l., 48.67661° N, 25.85291° E; 22.06.2018, 1 ♂; 192 m a.s.l., 48.68012° N, 25.85049° E; 22.06.2018, 1 ♂, 171 m a.s.l., 48.67120° N, 25.85270° E; 23.06.2018, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy, Kyiv, Ternopil.

***Cratyna (Cratyna) subalpina* (Mohrig & Mamaev, 1990)**

Mohrig, Krivosheina & Mamaev, 1990; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Cratyna (Peyerimhoffia) vagabunda* (Winnertz 1867)**

(Fig. 10)

Babytskiy, Zuieva & Bezsmertna, 2018b; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Volia, 352 m a.s.l., 49.40038° N, 25.62152° E; 02.07.2018, 2 ♂; **Volyn:** near Klubochyn, 204 m a.s.l., 50.96230° N, 25.83071° E; 27.06.2017, 1 ♂; near Zhabka, 218 m a.s.l., 50.81591° N, 25.43467° E; 29.06.2017, 1 ♂, 205 m a.s.l., 50.82380° N, 25.42934° E; 29.06.2017, 3 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Odesa, Volyn.

Ctenosciara hyalipennis* (Meigen, 1804) (Fig. 11)

Material. Ternopil: near Strusiv, 349 m a.s.l., 49.33878° N, 25.63311° E; 19.06.2018, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Klubochyn, 204 m a.s.l., 50.96230° N, 25.83071° E; 27.06.2017, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Volyn.

***Epidapus (Epidapus) atomarius* (De Geer, 1778)**

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Lviv: near Stare Selo, 340 m a.s.l., 49.21899° N, 24.40241° E; 13.08.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Lviv.

***Epidapus (Epidapus) alnicola* (Tuomikoski, 1957)**

Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Epidapus (Epidapus) detriticola* (Kratochvil, 1936)

Material. Ternopil: near Luchka, 375 m a.s.l., 49.40917° N, 25.61360° E; 07.05.2017, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

Epidapus (Epidapus) gracilis* (Walker, 1848)

Material. Lviv: near Stare Selo, 340 m a.s.l., 49.21899° N, 24.40241° E; 13.08.2016, 8 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Lviv.

***Epidapus (Epidapus) lucifuga* Mohrig, 1970**

Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Epidapus (Epidapus) microthorax* (Börner, 1903)**

Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Epidapus (Epidapus) schillei* (Börner, 1903)

Material. Ternopil: Mykulyntsi, 296 m a.s.l., 49.40126° N, 25.60140° E; 19-21.06.2016, 1 ♂; near Luchka, 338 m a.s.l., 49.40483° N, 25.61241° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

***Epidapus (Pseudoptanogyna) carpaticus* (Mohrig & Mamaev, 1985)**

Mohrig et al. (1985); Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Hemineurina conspicua* (Winnertz, 1867)

Material. Ternopil: near Hlushka, 296 m a.s.l., 48.74407° N, 25.65329° E; 13.07.2015, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

***Hemineurina inflata* (Winnertz, 1867)**

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Luchka, 338 m a.s.l., 49.40437° N, 25.61119° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ternopil.

Hemineurina venosa* (Staeger, 1840) (Fig. 13)

Material. Ternopil: near Druzhba, 370 m a.s.l., 49.34526° N, 25.65677° E; 03.08.2017, 15 ♂; near Luchka, 359 m a.s.l., 49.40715° N, 25.61195° E; 20.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Strusiv, 408 m a.s.l., 49.34376° N, 25.62999° E; 30.06.2018, 2 ♂; near Volia, 352 m a.s.l., 49.40038° N, 25.62152° E; 02.07.2018, 3 ♂; **Volyn:** near Zhabka, 218 m a.s.l., 50.81591° N, 25.43467° E; 29.06.2017, 2 ♂, 228 m a.s.l., 50.81466° N, 25.42506° E; 29.06.2017, 3 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Volyn.

***Leptosciarella (Leptosciarella) pilosa* (Staeger, 1840)**

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Mohrig & Menzel, 1997; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Zakarpatska.

***Leptosciarella (Leptosciarella) scutellata* (Staeger, 1840) (Fig. 12)**

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Mohrig & Menzel, 1997; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Lviv: near Stare Selo, 340 m a.s.l., 49.21899° N, 24.40241° E; 13.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Rivne:** near Novosilky, 208 m a.s.l., 50.599260° N, 25.475941° E; 10.09.2017, 1 ♂; **Ternopil:** near Luchka, 329 m a.s.l., 49.40437° N, 25.61119° E; 07.05.2017, 3 ♂; 329 m a.s.l., 49.40440° N, 25.61105° E; 07.05.2017, 3 ♂; 338 m a.s.l., 49.40483° N, 25.61241° E; 07.05.2017, 2 ♂; 338 m a.s.l., 49.40493° N, 25.61218° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂; 375 m a.s.l., 49.40917° N, 25.61360° E; 07.05.2017, 2 ♂; near Luchka, 338 m a.s.l., 49.40443° N, 25.61215° E; 27.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Strusiv, 408 m a.s.l., 49.34376° N, 25.62999° E; 30.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Strusiv, 378 m a.s.l., 49.33495° N, 25.63931° E; 30.06.2018,

2 ♂; **Volyn:** near Sokyrychi, 209 m a.s.l., 50.87516° N, 25.51393° E; 28.06.2017, 3 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Cherkasy, Kyiv, Lviv, Rivne, Ternopil, Volyn, Zakarpatska.

***Leptosciarella (Leptosciarella) subpilosa* (Edwards, 1925)**

Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Leptosciarella (Leptosciarella) trochanterata* (Zetterstedt, 1851)

Material. Ternopil: near Kasperivtsi, 171 m a.s.l., 48.67120° N, 25.85270° E; 24.06.2018, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** Turiisk, 154 m a.s.l., 51.07981° N, 24.52999° E; 04.07.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Volyn.

***Lycoriella ingenua* (Dufour, 1839)**

Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2019, 2022.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: Rybne, 379 m a.s.l., 48.934796° N, 24.577489° E; 23.10.2019, 1 ♂; 12.11.2019, 2 ♂; **Volyn:** Turiisk, 150 m a.s.l., 51.080061° N, 24.530237° E; 10.04.2015, 1 ♂, 150 m a.s.l., 51.080076° N, 24.530083° E; 10.04.2015, 1 ♂, 186 m a.s.l., 51.079953° N, 24.530273° E; 08.10.2016, 4 ♂, 3 ♀ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk, Volyn.

***Lycoriella latilobata* Menzel & Mohrig, 2000**

Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

***Lycoriella lundstromi* (Frey, 1948) (Fig. 14)**

Babytskiy & Bezsmertna, 2021; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: Nastasiv, 324 m a.s.l., 49.41884° N, 25.51873° E; 19.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Luchka, 342 m a.s.l., 49.40665° N, 25.61123° E; 20.06.2018, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Klubochyn, 213 m a.s.l., 50.96447° N, 25.77727° E — 50.96230° N, 25.83071° E; 27.06.2017, 5 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Volyn.

***Lycoriella sativae* (Johannsen, 1912)**

Babytskiy, Rubanovska & Bezsmertna, 2022..

Material. Ternopil: Mykulyntsi, 296 m a.s.l., 49.40126° N, 25.60140° E; 19-21.06.2016, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** Turiisk, 154 m a.s.l., 51.07981° N, 24.52999° E; 04.07.2017, 1 ♂; near Turiisk, 169 m a.s.l., 51.06994° N, 24.54540° E; 05.07.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil, Volyn.

***Pnyxia scabiei* (Hopkins 1895)**

Gerbachevskaja, 1963; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Osmola, 1970; Babytskiy et al., 2019, 2022.

Material. Ternopil: Mykulyntsi, 296 m a.s.l., 49.40126° N, 25.60140° E; 19-21.06.2016, 1 ♂; 317 m a.s.l., 49.40124° N, 25.60146° E, 02-06.08.2017, 2 ♂; 15-21.06.2019, 2 ♂; 336 m a.s.l., 49.40123° N, 25.60143° E; 04-10.07.2021, 8 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Western regions exclude Carpathian, Ternopil.

***Pseudolycoriella (Pseudolycoriella) brunnea* (Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936)**

Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936; Mohrig et al., 1979; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Skomorokhy, 203 m a.s.l., 48.90773° N, 25.39594° E; 09.08.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ternopil, Zakarpatska.

Pseudolycoriella (Pseudolycoriella) paludum (Frey, 1948) (Fig. 15)

Babytskiy & Bezsmertna, 2021; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: between Lucka and Volia, 337 m a.s.l., 49.40572° N, 25.61362° E; 03.07.2015, 1 ♂; Luchka, 324 m a.s.l., 49.40420° N, 25.61105° E; 18.06.2018, 3 ♂; Luchka, 330 m a.s.l., 49.40447° N, 25.61140° E; 18.06.2018, 1 ♂; Luchka, 343 m a.s.l., 49.40451° N, 25.61254° E; 18.06.2018, 4 ♂; near Strusiv, 355 m a.s.l., 49.33839° N, 25.63538° E; 19.06.2018, 3 ♂, 374 m a.s.l., 49.33638° N, 25.63387° E; 19.06.2018, 6 ♂; near Luchka, 338 m a.s.l., 49.40443° N, 25.61215° E; 27.06.2018, 1 ♂; 350 m a.s.l., 49.40638° N, 25.61746° E; 27.06.2018, 2 ♂; near Druzhba, 370 m a.s.l., 49.34654° N, 25.66220° E; 28.06.2018, 3 ♂; near Strusiv, 408 m a.s.l., 49.34376° N, 25.62999° E; 30.06.2018, 3 ♂; 378 m a.s.l., 49.33495° N, 25.63931° E; 30.06.2018, 2 ♂; near Volia, 376 m a.s.l., 49.38887° N, 25.62857° E; 02.07.2018, 8 ♂; 361 m a.s.l., 49.38776° N, 25.62919° E; 02.07.2018; 13 ♂; 346 m a.s.l., 49.38903° N, 25.62634° E; 02.07.2018, 1 ♂; 352 m a.s.l., 49.40038° N, 25.62152° E; 02.07.2018, 6 ♂; **Volyn:** near Klubochyn, 214 m a.s.l., 50.96483° N, 25.77776° E; 27.06.2017, 3 ♂, 213 m a.s.l., 50.96447° N, 25.77727° E; 27.06.2017, 5 ♂, 212 m a.s.l., 50.96522° N, 25.77657° E; 27.06.2017, 2 ♂, 204 m a.s.l., 50.96230° N, 25.83071° E; 27.06.2017, 2 ♂; near Sokyrychi, 209 m a.s.l., 50.87516° N, 25.51393° E; 28.06.2017, 5 ♂; Between Berestiane and Kholonevychi, 175 m a.s.l., 50.99890° N, 25.93088° E; 28.06.2017, 8 ♂; near Turiisk, 180 m a.s.l., 51.06977° N, 24.54502° E; 05.07.2017, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Kyiv, Volyn, Ternopil.

Scatopsciara (Scatopsciara) bucera Rudzinski, 1994*

Material. Ternopil: near Luchka, 338 m a.s.l., 49.40483° N, 25.61241° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂; 375 m a.s.l., 49.40917° N, 25.61360° E; 07.05.2017, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

Scatopsciara (Scatopsciara) calamophila Frey, 1948

Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Khmelnytskyi: near Hrushka, 131 m a.s.l., 48.57664° N, 26.99941° E; 03.05.2015, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Khmelnytskyi.

Scatopsciara (Scatopsciara) multispina (Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936)

Bukowski & Lengersdorf, 1936; Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ternopil: near Volia, 319 m a.s.l., 49.38771° N, 25.62899° E; 04.07.2015, 3 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ternopil.

Scatopsciara (Scatopsciara) neglecta Menzel & Mohrig, 1998

Menzel & Mohrig, 1998; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Scatopsciara (Xenopygina) curvilinea (Lengersdorf, 1934)*

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: Between Nezvesko and Luka, 168 m a.s.l., 48.78383° N, 25.25209° E; 10.08.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk.

Schwenckfeldina carbonaria (Meigen 1830)

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: Between Nezvesko and Luka, 196 m a.s.l., 48.78303° N, 25.25203° E; 10.08.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv.

Sciara analis Schiner, 1864

Nowicki, 1864, 1865; Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Antonova, 1978; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022; Komarova, 2022; Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: near Bystrytsia, 704 m a.s.l.; 48.49014° N, 24.27940° E; 04.08.2020, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ivano-Frankivsk, Lviv.

Sciara flavimana Zetterstedt, 1851

Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Material. Rivne: near Horodets, 158 m a.s.l., 51.27655° N, 26.36690° E; 10.08.2021, 1 ♂; **Ternopil:** near Zhnyborody, 266 m a.s.l., 48.89407° N, 25.44164° E; 20.07.2019, 1 ♂; to South of Beremiany, 324 m a.s.l., 48.87431° N, 25.43947° E; 26.06.2021, 1 ♂; 324 m a.s.l., 48.87431° N, 25.43947° E; 28.06.2021, 2 ♂; between Kasperivtsi and Holihrydy, 243 m a.s.l., 48.68757° N, 25.87442° E; 27.06.2021, 4 ♂; **Volyn:** near Kholonevychi, 173 m a.s.l., 51.00889° N, 25.92952° E; 13.08.2020, 3 ♂; near Solovychi, 187 m a.s.l., 51.06278° N, 24.48196° E; 25.06.2022, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Rivne, Ternopil, Volyn.

Sciara hebes (Loew, 1869)

Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Material. Ternopil: near Krovinka, 353 m a.s.l., 49.33741° N, 25.67169° E; 19.06.2019, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

Sciara helvola Winnertz, 1867

Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Material. Chernivtsi: near Novodnistrovsk, 149 m a.s.l., 48.58870° N, 27.45185° E; 21.06.2021; 26 ♂; near Spaska, 440 m a.s.l., 48.29888° N, 25.77772° E; 22.06.2021; 15 ♂; **Ternopil:** near Babytsi, 222 m a.s.l., 48.65057° N, 26.04671° E; 25.06.2021, 2 ♂; between Kasperivtsi and Holihrydy, 243 m a.s.l., 48.68757° N, 25.87442° E; 27.06.2021, 9 ♂; to South of Beremiany, 324 m a.s.l., 48.87431° N, 25.43947° E; 28.06.2021, 2 ♂; **Volyn:** between Zhuravychi and Klubochyn, 198 m a.s.l., 50.96952° N, 25.75357° E; 28.06.2022; 20 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Cherkasy, Chernivtsi, Ternopil, Vinnytsia and Volyn.

Sciara hemerobioides (Scopoli, 1763)

Nowicki, 1864, 1865; Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Antonova, 1978; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022; Komarova, 2022; Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: between Nezvesko and Luka, 196 m a.s.l., 48.78303° N, 25.25203° E; 10.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Ternopil:** near Volia, 319 m a.s.l., 49.38771° N, 25.62899° E; 04.07.2015, 1 ♀; outskirts of Mykulyntsi, 293 m a.s.l., 49.40361° N, 25.60682° E; 27.06.2018, 1 ♀; near Nyrkiv, 230 m a.s.l., 48.82221° N, 25.57476° E; 22.07.2019, 1 ♂; Zalitsi, 316 m a.s.l., 49.79788° N, 25.37057° E; 01.08.2022, 2 ♂; **Zakarpatska:** near Mala Uholka, 475 m a.s.l., 48.25609° N, 23.62223° E; 02.08.2019, 1 ♂, 691 m a.s.l., 48.26364° N, 23.61694° E; 02.08.2019, 9 ♂, 607 m a.s.l., 48.26694° N, 23.62933° E; 03.08.2019, 1 ♂, 546 m a.s.l., 48.26625° N, 23.62984° E; 03.08.2019, 7 ♂, 541 m a.s.l., 48.26942° N, 23.63465° E; 04.08.2019, 2 ♂, 527 m a.s.l., 48.26954° N, 23.63552° E; 04.08.2019, 1 ♂, 602 m a.s.l., 48.27708° N, 23.64047° E; 04.08.2019, 1 ♂; near Velyka Uholka, 839 m a.s.l., 48.25619° N, 23.67759° E; 05.08.2019, 3 ♂; near

Mala Uholka, 546 m a.s.l., 48.2665° N, 23.62984° E; 06.08.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ivano-Frankivsk, Lviv, Ternopil, Zakarpatska.

Sciara humeralis Zetterstedt, 1851

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Antonova, 1978; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022; Komarova, 2022; Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Material. Volyn: near Vorotniv, 232 m a.s.l., 50.72240° N, 25.56622° E; 16.08.2019, 3 ♂; near Berestiane, 176 m a.s.l., 50.97375° N, 25.94138° E; 12.08.2020, 2 ♂, 182 m a.s.l., 50.94063° N, 25.95123° E; 12.08.2020, 1 ♂, 182 m a.s.l., 50.94215° N, 25.95353° E; 12.08.2020, 1 ♂, 182 m a.s.l., 50.97194° N, 25.94257° E; 13.08.2020, 3 ♂; near Nevir, 219 m a.s.l., 51.86719° N, 24.98927° E; 07.08.2021, 5 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Volyn.

Sciara incerta Winnertz, 1867

Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Material. Ternopil: near Kasperivtsi, 171 m a.s.l., 48.67120° N, 25.85270° E; 22.06.2018, 1 ♂, 171 m a.s.l., 48.67120° N, 25.85270° E; 24.06.2018, 1 ♂; near Babyntsi, 246 m a.s.l., 48.64989° N, 26.05343° E; 25.06.2021, 1 ♂; 228 m a.s.l., 48.64970° N, 26.05253° E; 25.06.2021, 2 ♂; to South of Beremiany, 324 m a.s.l., 48.87431° N, 25.43947° E; 26.06.2021, 3 ♂; between Kasperivtsi and Holihrady, 243 m a.s.l., 48.68757° N, 25.87442° E; 27.06.2021, 4 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ternopil.

Sciara militaris Nowicki, 1868

Verkhatskyi, 1864; Nowicki, 1868; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022; Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Distribution in Ukraine: Lviv, Ivano-Frankivsk.

Sciara ruficauda Meigen, 1818

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Antonova, 1978; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022; Komarova, 2022; Babytskiy, Pavliuk & Bezsmertna, 2023.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: near Bystrytsia, 1427 m a.s.l., 48.46648° N, 24.32005° E; 05.08.2020, 1 ♂; **Volyn:** near Berestiane, 182 m a.s.l., 50.97194° N, 25.94257° E; 13.08.2020, 1 ♂; near Trostianets and Yaromel, 226 m a.s.l., 50.96214° N, 25.59570° E; 27.06.2022, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Volyn.

Trichosia (Trichosia) confusa Menzel & Mohrig, 1997

Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Menzel & Mohrig, 2000; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Zakarpatska.

Trichosia (Trichosia) flavicoxa Tuomikoski, 1960

Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Trichosia (Trichosia) morio (Fabricius, 1794)

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Zakarpatska.

Xylosciara (Xylosciara) heptacantha Tuomikoski, 1957

Babytskiy & Bezsmertna, 2021; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: between Nezvesko and Luka, 196 m a.s.l., 48.78303° N, 25.25203° E; 10.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Ternopil:** near Stinka, 200 m a.s.l., 48.91482° N, 25.23508° E; 09.08.2016, 1 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk, Kyiv, Ternopil.

Xylosciara (Xylosciara) phryganophila (Frey, 1948)

Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Xylosciara (Xylosciara) spinata (Pettey, 1918)

Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Hippa & Vilkamaa, 2004; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Zygoneura (Pharetrata) bidens (Mamaev, 1968)

Mamaev, 1968; Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, 1986; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Distribution in Ukraine: Zakarpatska.

Zygoneura (Zygoneura) sciarina Meigen, 1830

Gerbachevskaja, 1969; Krivosheina & Mohrig, 1986; Babytskiy et al., 2022.

Material. Ivano-Frankivsk: between Nezvesko and Luka, 196 m a.s.l., 48.78303° N, 25.25203° E; 10.08.2016, 1 ♂; **Ternopil:** between Zahaitsi and Novosilka, 328 m a.s.l., 49.27673° N, 25.17162° E; 19.06.2016, 1 ♀; **Zakarpatska:** near Mala Uholka, 691 m a.s.l., 48.26364° N, 23.61694° E; 02.08.2019, 2 ♂ (Babytskiy) (SIZK).

Distribution in Ukraine: Crimea, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ternopil, Zakarpatska.

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References

- Antonova, E. B. 1978. Review of black fungus gnats from genus *Sciara* Meigen (Diptera, Sciaridae) of the USSR fauna. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie*, 57(1): 180–187. (In Russian)
- Babytskiy, A. I. & Bezsmertna, O. O. 2021. New Records of Sciarid Species (Diptera, Sciaridae) from Ukraine. III. *Zoodiversity*, 55(6): 493–504. <https://doi.org/10.15407/zoo2021.06.493>
- Babytskiy, A. I., Bezsmertna, O. O., Moroz, M. S., Pavliuk, S. D. & Honcharenko, B. V. 2020. New Records of *Bradysia* Species (Diptera, Sciaridae) from Ukraine. *Zoodiversity*, 54(4): 329–340. <https://doi.org/10.15407/zoo2020.04.329>

- Babytskiy, A. I., Bezsmertna, O. O., Protsenko, Y. V., Pavliuk, S. D. & Rubanovska, N. V. 2022. Biodiversity of Sciaridae (Diptera) in Ukraine. *Biosystems Diversity*, 30(1): 12–21. <https://doi.org/10.15421/012202>
- Babytskiy, A. I., Moroz, M. S., Kalashnyk, S. O., Bezsmertna, O. O., Dudiak, I. D. & Voitsekhivska, O. V. 2019. New findings of pest sciarid species (Diptera, Sciaridae) in Ukraine, with the first record of *Bradysia difformis*. *Biosystems Diversity*, 27(2): 131–141. <http://doi.org/10.15421/011918>
- Babytskiy, A. I., Pavliuk, S. D. & Bezsmertna, O. O. 2023. Review of the Genus *Sciara* Meigen, 1803 (Diptera, Sciaridae) in Ukraine. *Insects*, 14(9): 732. <https://doi.org/10.3390/insects14090732>
- Babytskiy, A. I., Rubanovska, N. V. & Bezsmertna, O. O. 2022. New records of sciarid species (Diptera, Sciaridae) from Ukraine. IV. *Zoo-diversity*, 56(6): 435–446. <https://doi.org/10.15407/zoo2022.06.435>
- Babytskiy, A. I., Zuieva, O. A. & Bezsmertna, O. O. 2018a. *Corynoptera membranigera* (Kieffer, 1903) – new sciarid species (Diptera, Sciaridae) for entomofauna of Ukraine. In: *Proceedings of the scientific and practical conference Ternopil Bioscience – 2018, dedicated to 20th anniversary of foundation of Holytskii biostation of Volodymyr Hnatiuk Ternopil National Pedagogical University*. Vektor, Ternopil: 66–68.
- Babytskiy, A. I., Zuieva, O. A. & Bezsmertna, O. O. 2018b. *Peyerimhoffia vagabunda* – new sciarid species (Sciaridae, Diptera) for the entomofauna of Ukraine. *Biosystems Diversity*, 26(3): 245–249. <https://doi.org/10.15421/011837>
- Babytskiy, A. I., Zuieva, O. A., Bezsmertna, O. O. & Dudiak, I. D. 2019. The first records of *Corynoptera* species (Diptera, Sciaridae) from Ukraine. *Vestnik Zoologii*, 53(3): 227–236. <https://doi.org/10.2478/vzoo-2019-0022>
- Bukowski, W. & Lengersdorf, F. 1936. Neue Lycoriiden-Arten aus der Krim. *Konowia*, 15(1–2): 106–112.
- Camaño Portela, J. L., Pino Pérez, J. J., Pino Pérez, R. & Silva-Pando, F. J. 2008. Contributions to the knowledge of Diptera in NW Spain. *Boletín BIGA*, 4: 91–94.
- Gerbachevskaja, A. A. 1963. Leaf midges (Diptera, Lycoriidae) injurious to vegetables and common mushrooms in hothouses of Leningrad region. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie*, 42(3): 496–511. (In Russian)
- Gerbachevskaja, A. A. 1969. 25. Sciaridae family. In: Bei-Bienko, G. Ya., ed. *Opredelitel nasekomykh evropejskoj chasti SSSR*, 5(1). Nauka, Leningrad: 320–356. (In Russian)
- Gerbachevskaja-Pavluchenko, A. A. 1986. Family Sciaridae. In: Soós, Á. & L. Papp, L., eds. *Catalogue of Palaearctic Diptera*, 4. Akadémiai Kiadó, Budapest: 11–72.
- Hippa, H., Vilkamaa, P. & Heller, K. 2010. Review of Holarctic *Corynoptera* Winnertz, 1867, s. str. (Diptera, Sciaridae). *Zootaxa*, 2695: 1–197. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2695.1.1>
- Hippa, H. & Vilkamaa, P. 1994. The genus *Camptochaeta* gen. n. (Diptera, Sciaridae). *Acta Zoologica Fennica*, 194: 1–85.
- Hippa, H. & Vilkamaa, P. 2004. The genus *Xylosciara* Tuomikoski (Diptera, Sciaridae): Phylogeny and review of the species. *Acta Zoologica Fennica*, 214: 1–38.
- Hippa, H., Vilkamaa, P. & Mohrig, W. 2003. Phylogeny of *Corynoptera* Winnertz and related genera, with the description of *Claustropyga* gen. nov. (Diptera, Sciaridae). *Studia dipterologica*, 9(2): 469–511.
- Komarova, L. A. & Komarov, S. S. 2022. A review of sciarids of the genus *Sciara* Meigen (Diptera, Sciaridae) of the Altai fauna, with description of one new species. *Bulletin of the Altai Branch of the Russian Geographical Society*, 1: 68–88. (In Russian)
- Krivosheina, N. P. & Mohrig, W. K. 1986. Diptera from Sciaridae family of the European part of the USSR. *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie*, 65(4): 153–163. (In Russian)
- Mamaev, B. M. 1968. New nematoceros Diptera of the USSR fauna (Diptera, Axymyiidae, Mycetobiidae, Sciaridae, Cecidomyiidae). *Entomologicheskoe obozrenie*, 47(3): 605–616. (In Russian)
- Menzel, F. & Mohrig, W. 1998. Beiträge zur Taxonomie und Faunistik der paläarktischen Trauermücken (Diptera, Sciaridae). Teil VI – Neue Ergebnisse aus Typenuntersuchungen und die daraus resultierenden taxonomisch-nomenklatorischen Konsequenzen. *Studia dipterologica*, 5(2): 351–378.
- Menzel, F. & Mohrig, W. 2000. Revision der palaarktischen Trauermücken (Diptera: Sciaridae). *Studia dipterologica, Supplement 6 (1999)*: 1–761.
- Mohrig, W. & Menzel, F. 1997. Revision der paläarktischen Arten von *Trichosia* Winnertz sensu Tuomikoski, 1960 (Diptera, Sciaridae). Teil II. Gattungen ‘*Leptosciarella*’ Tuomikoski, 1960 und ‘*Trichodapus*’ gen. nov. *Studia Dipterologica*, 4(1): 41–98.²
- Mohrig, W., Heller, K., Hippa, H., Vilkamaa, P. & Menzel, F. 2012. Revision of the Black Fungus Gnats (Diptera: Sciaridae) of North America. *Studia dipterologica*, 19(1/2): 141–286.
- Mohrig, W., Krivosheina, N. & Mamaev, B. 1989a. Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Trauermücken (Diptera, Sciaridae) der Sowjetunion. Teil XII: Gattung *Bradysia*, Serie 1. *Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Ökologie und Geographie der Tiere*, 116(4): 411–425.
- Mohrig, W., Krivosheina, N. & Mamaev, B. 1989b. Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Trauermücken (Diptera, Sciaridae) der Sowjetunion. Teil XIII: Gattung *Bradysia*, Serie 2. *Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Ökologie und Geographie der Tiere*, 116(4): 427–445.⁴
- Mohrig, W., Krivosheina, N. & Mamaev, B. 1990. Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Trauermücken (Diptera, Sciaridae) der Sowjetunion. Teil XIV: Gattungen *Plastosciara*, *Lycoriella* und *Scatopsiara*. *Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Ökologie und Geographie der Tiere*, 117(1): 11–21.
- Mohrig, W., Krivosheina, N. & Mamaev, B. 1985. Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Trauermücken (Diptera, Sciaridae) der Sowjetunion. Teil 8: Neune Arten aus europäischen Gebieten. Mit 12 Abbildungen. *Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Ökologie und Geographie der Tiere*, 112(3): 299–310.
- Mohrig, W., Mamaev, B. M. & Krivosheina, N. P. 1979. Neue Arten holzverwertender Sciariden (Diptera) aus der UdSSR. *Zoologische Jahrbücher, Abteilung für Systematik, Ökologie und Geographie der Tiere*, 106: 572–588.
- Nowicki, M. 1864. *Przyczynek do owadniczej fauny Galicyi*. W Drukarni Uniwersyteckiej, Krakow: 1–87.
- Nowicki, M. 1865. *Insecta Haliciae Musei Dzieduszyckiani*. Typis Universitatis Jagellonicae, Krakow: 1–87.
- Nowicki, M. 1868. O plenu kopalińskim i łączącym się z niego pleniówce, *Sciara militaris* n. sp. *Rocznik Towarzystwa Naukowego Krakowskiego*, 37: 1–109.
- Osmola, N. I. 1970. Morphology of imaginal and preimaginal phases of *Pnyxia scabiei* Hopk. (Diptera, Sciaridae). *Entomologicheskoe Obozrenie*, 49(4): 770–775. (In Russian)⁶
- Rudzinski, H. G. & Ševčík, J. 2012. Fungus gnats (Diptera: Sciaroidea) of the Gemer region (Central Slovakia): Part 3 – Sciaridae. *Časopis Slezského zemského muzea*, 61: 143–157.
- Verkhratskiy, I. 1864. *Beginning to the verification of the nomenclature and folk terminology of natural history*. M. F. Poremba, Lviv: 1–18. (In Ukrainian)
- Winnertz, J. 1868. Acht neue Arten der Gattung *Sciara*. *Verhandlungen der Zoologisch-Botanischen Gesellschaft in Wien*, 18: 533–540.